

Fabrication of SiC Fiber-Reinforced 3D Woven Composites Using Tow Sizing and Optimized Preform Structures

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Expansion of application fields of ceramic matrix composite (CMC)

CMC exhaust nozzles in F135 aero engine

Materials Science and Engineering 678 (2019) 012043

SiC/SiC CMC combustor liner by SNECMA

Materials Science and Engineering 678 (2019) 012043

SiC/SiC turbine guide vane before and after hot test

Materials Science and Engineering 678 (2019) 012043

Strength and temperature data for ceramics and metal alloys

Annu Rev Mater Res, 38 (1) (2008), pp. 425-443

Need for 3-Dimensional SiC_f/SiC composite

SiC/SiC complex three-dimensional structure

Materials Science and Engineering 678 (2019) 012043

Examples of three-dimensional woven structures

Journal of the European Ceramic Society 44 (2024) 116739

- SiC_f/SiC composites are prized in aerospace for their superior oxidation resistance
- Although **3D weaving** is essential for fabricating **complex structures**, process challenges mean composites are implemented in 2D or 2.5D architectures

High-Temperature stability of Tyranno SA fiber

Tensile strength and creep resistance at high T

Journal of Materials Science & Technology 35 (2019) 2743–2750

Change in composite thermal conductivity at high T

Journal of Nuclear Materials 329–333 (2004) 497–501

- Tyranno SA fiber maintains higher tensile strength and creep stability at high temperatures compared to other fibers
- Its thermal conductivity is higher than other fibers, making it advantageous in fields like nuclear energy where thermal diffusion is crucial

SiC fibers susceptible to friction

Comparison of Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) images of SiC fibers

Journal of the European Ceramic Society 32 (2012) 547–557

Comparison of Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) images of SiC fibers

Journal of the European Ceramic Society 32 (2012) 547–557

- Tyranno fibers are produced at higher temperatures than other fibers, resulting in **greater crystallinity** and thus **superior thermal properties**
- However, this causes the fiber surface to be extremely **rough**, resulting in severe **abrasion damage** and increased fiber brittleness

Low flexibility of SiC fibers

Low flexibility of SiC fibers (UBE-SA3)

- SiC fibers have **high brittleness**, resulting in much **lower fracture strain** compared to carbon fibers, which are commonly used in weaving

UBE TYRANNO-SA Grade 3

Nominal properties	
Atomic composition	SiC O,Al < 0.008
Tensile strength (GPa) ^a	2.8
Tensile modulus (GPa) ^a	420
Elongation (%)	0.7
Density (g/cm ³)	3.02
Fibre diameter (μm)	10
Thermal conductivity (W/m K)	64.6 (at 25 °C)

Materials Science & Engineering A 638 (2015) 305–313

FIBER PROPERTIES Toray T700

PROPERTY	ENGLISH	METRIC	METHOD
Tensile Strength	711 ksi	4,900 MPa	TY-030B-01
Tensile Modulus	34.8 Msi	240 GPa	TY-030B-01
Strain at Failure		2.0%	TY-030B-01
Density		1.80 g/cm ³	TY-030B-02
Filament Diameter		7 μm	
Yield	12K	800 g/1000m	TY-030B-03

T700G Rev. 5: Updated April 13, 2018

Research strategy - Covering

Polymers 2024, 16(17), 2476

- Goal of the covering process is to enhance the mechanical properties of the tow, including bending strength, and increase friction resistance
- SA3 tow was covered with PET, and SA4 tow was covered with PLA. In the case of SA3, an inner core was added beneath the covering, and both were compared together

Research objective

- To examine the strengthening effect at the tow level when covering is applied
- To assess the effect of covering in the weaving process and understand its impact on the material properties at the composite level

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Experiment – Tow level property

Ceramic tow tensile test (ISO 22459)

Journal of the European Ceramic Society 42 (2022) 1928–1937

Kawabata bending test

Sinclair loop test (Maximum curvature)

Advanced Composite Materials, 8:3, 281-291

3D Weaving machine

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Morphological analysis of covered SiC tow

PET core covering

None core covering

- Both covered samples were processed successfully with minimal damage
- Friction during the process caused slight fly debris
- The sample without a core showed more damage due to increased frictional impact

Tensile test results – SA3

Pure Tyranno SA3

PET core and PET covering

Noncore and PET covering

- After covering, both tensile strength and strain significantly increased
- Failure morphology changed from irregular stress reduction to sudden failure

Mechanism of property enhancement through covering

Slip failure of SiC ceramic tow

Composites Part A 146 (2021) 106426)

Transverse compressive stress due to covering and simultaneously failure after covering

Journal of Industrial Textiles 47(8)

- In the uncovered tow, the fibers are held together only by weak physical bonds, so slip dominates the failure behavior
- Once a covering is applied, however, transverse compressive stresses promote efficient stress transfer between fibers, making fiber fracture the primary failure mode

Tensile test results – SA4

- SA4 exhibits more **uniform fiber properties** and superior sizing compared to SA3, resulting in significantly **less tow slip**
- Nevertheless, when **covered**, it demonstrates a **strengthening effect**, with both stress and strain increasing by approximately 25%

Increase in bending resistance

- Following covering, the added thickness of the covering yarn enhances bending resistance
- And the inclusion of low-elasticity polymer fibers leads to greater energy dissipation, thereby increasing hysteresis

Increase in maximum curvature

- By facilitating the redistribution of stresses that occur during bending and thereby delaying failure, the maximum curvature increases
- A high maximum curvature enables the fabrication of complex structures in 3D weaving

Enhanced weavability resulting from covering

Tyranno SA3 woven

Tyranno SA3 and covering woven

SA3	Held 1 Z-binder	Held 2 Fixed warp	Held 3 Fixed warp	Held 4 Z-binder	Held 5 Fixed warp	Held 6 Fixed warp	Held 7 Fixed warp	Held 8 Z-binder
Remaining tows	5/15	0/15	12/15	0/15	14/15	11/15	13/15	9/15

PET cover	Held 1 Fixed warp	Held 2 Z-binder	Held 3 Fixed warp	Held 4 Z-binder	Held 5 Fixed warp	Held 6 Z-binder	Held 7 Fixed warp	Held 8 Z-binder
Remaining tows	15/15	9/15	15/15	0/15	15/15	9/15	15/15	3/15

- Pure SA3 suffered significant friction-induced damage over roughly 10 cm of weaving, whereas the covering tow used as the fixed warp incurred zero losses

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Conclusions

- I. As aerospace activities intensify, research into SiC 3D-woven ceramic composites capable of fabricating complex structures is essential**
- II. However, because SiC fibers are inherently brittle and have poor weavability, fiber reinforcement processes are required**
- III. Applying a polymer-fiber covering to the SiC tow resulted in increases in various tow-scale properties**
- IV. Friction-induced damage and failure during the weaving process were greatly reduced, and composite-scale property changes will be measured subsequently**

Thank you

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